

Figure 1S. Maximum Likelihood tree (log-likelihood = -55466.6408) depicting the phylogenetic relationships of Cercosaurinae. SH-aLRT and Ultrafast Bootstrap values are shown on the left, respectively. Support values ≥ 80 for SH-aLRT and ≥ 95 for UB are represented by an asterisk.